

Introduction: Molecular nanotechnology is an emerging field in medicine that is rapidly developing to provide innovative solutions to the complex issues related to skull base and cerebrovascular illnesses. Scientists are exploring the unique characteristics of nanoparticles, such as their ability to penetrate the blood-brain barrier (BBB), to revolutionize diagnostics and therapies in the crucial domains of neuro-oncology and neurology.

Discussion: Molecular nanotechnology presents a promising approach to address neuro vascular and neuro-oncology disorders by using nanoparticles to improve diagnosis and treatment. We reviewed some articles on pubmed with these keywords: nanotechnology, acute ischemic stroke, treatment plans, diagnosis, stroke management, brain tumor diagnosis, brain tumor treatment

Nanotechnology and the Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB)

The BBB severely hampers effective drug transport to the brain. However, by getting beyond this obstacle, nanomaterials present a viable remedy. Precision targeting, a large drug load, and biocompatibility are just a few of the many functions that engineered nanoparticles exhibit. These qualities allow for more effective therapeutic delivery to the brain parenchyma. (Figure 1)

Ischemic Stroke Management

Endovascular treatment (EVT) and intravenous tissue plasminogen activator (IV-tPA) have been the GOLD standard methods of acute ischemic stroke (AIS) management historically. Nanotechnology can now enhance these methods, which provides advanced drug-delivery vehicles such as liposomes and biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles. These solutions improve outcomes, reduce hazards, and lengthen the therapeutic window for stroke patients.

Ischemic Stroke Diagnosis

The substantial global health burden of ischemic strokes calls for improvements in diagnosis methods. A variety of nanoparticles, including iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIOs) and perfluorocarbon nanoparticles (PFC-NPs), enable enhanced imaging modalities for accurate diagnosis and prompt management. Nanoparticles are valuable biomarkers for early stroke identification.

Figure 1: Delivery channels for nano-carriers through the blood-brain barrier © 2018 by the authors.

Real-Time Monitoring and Progression

Nanotechnology enables real-time tracking of the course of an ischemic stroke, providing information on the causes of the condition and the effectiveness of treatment. Technological developments, including anti-Iba-1-targeted superparamagnetic iron-platinum nanoparticles, allow for the spatiotemporal tracking of neuro-inflammatory responses following stroke, providing information for tailored treatment approaches.

Conclusion: With its unparalleled potential for improved diagnostics and tailored treatments, nanotechnology has the potential to completely change the way that skull base disorders and cerebrovascular events are managed. These new scientific advancements will ultimately lead to more favorable patient outcomes.

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